

**EXPERIENCES OF INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN STUDYING,
RECOGNITION AND IMPROVING THE IMPACT OF SINGAPORE'S SOCIAL
POLICY ON MODERN EDUCATION AND PEDAGOGICAL PROSPECTS.**

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Abstract: Today, education is a decisive factor of economic and scientific-technical development, formation of the social structure of the society, distribution of social statuses in it mechanism. At the same time, this is the educational system in foreign countries personnel with high knowledge and skills through development and improvement it can be understood that special attention is paid to preparation. For example, Singapore is one of the countries that invests heavily in education and achieves high results. This article provides information on the experiences of international cooperation in studying, recognizing and improving the impact of Singapore's social policy on modern education and pedagogical perspective.

Key words: education system, Singapore, miracle, cluster, special, express, academic, higher education, result.

Singapore's education system aims to bring out the best in every child. We seek to nurture the whole child and develop them into lifelong learners, with an enduring core of competencies to thrive in the 21st century. Our multiple educational pathways cater to the different strengths and interests of every student. Our schools provide a rich diversity of learning experiences for our students. On top of building a strong foundation in literacy and numeracy, we also cater to their educational needs in physical, aesthetic, moral, social and emotional aspects, and develop them holistically. Besides academic learning, students can develop their interest and talent in music, arts, and sports through co-curricular programmes and outdoor education. These learning experiences also give them opportunities to hone their leadership skills, as well as social and emotional competencies. There are also opportunities for our students to contribute to communities through various Values-inAction programmes, which are an integral part of school life as well as Applied Learning experiences, which allows them to (i) learn by doing; (ii) learn about the real world; and (iii) learn for life. In addition, our schools offer education and career guidance to help our students discover their interests and strengths and choose the pathways that allow them to achieve their fullest potential.

Due to the great emphasis on public schools in Singapore, they are not inferior to private schools in terms of quality and modernity of education. According to information, 20 percent of the country's budget is spent on education development. Therefore, local residents are not very interested in private schools, on the contrary, they prefer to educate their children in public schools with all the conditions. The secondary education system in the country includes schools, technical schools and colleges. In 2000, Singapore's parliament passed a law on compulsory education for school-aged children. According to it, primary education is free and compulsory for all citizens of the country. Children are admitted to the school from the age of 6. Secondary education is divided into primary, secondary and pre-university stages. Primary education includes 4 years of basic training (grades 1-4) and 2 years of specialized training (grades 5-6). At the foundation stage, students are taught English, mother tongue (Chinese, Malay or Tamil) and mathematics. According to the choice of boys and girls, ethics, aesthetics, work, music and physical education lessons are

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also held. From the 3rd grade, natural sciences are added to the curriculum. After 4 years of education, children are divided into groups according to their ability to learn the mother tongue, English and mathematics, after entering a specialized training stage. In schools, students are given the opportunity to develop a personal examination system. This ensures that each child shows his abilities better. At the end of the exams, children will receive one of the elementary, standard and advanced levels in English and mother tongue, and one of the basic and standard levels in mathematics and natural sciences, depending on their ability. At the end of their studies, students take the final exam and receive a PSLE (Primary School Leaving Examination) certificate to move on to the next level of education.

Debate. Regarding the general education system in Singapore it is necessary to pay attention. Education in Singapore is at the forefront of public policy stands One of the main goals of Singapore Ministry of Education is students to identify their talent, to realize their potential, throughout their life It consists in helping to develop interest and striving for knowledge. Singapore Education System - Education is not preparation for life, but life itself based on the principle. Singapore's general education system consists of three levels. The country is administrative. It is divided into 4 educational regions, each region consists of 7 school clusters consists of. The bilingual policy, a cornerstone of our education system, requires students to offer two languages: English Language and an official Mother Tongue Language. This enables them to connect with people from different backgrounds in a multi-cultural environment, and allow them to thrive in a diverse, globalised world. It also equips them with the language and cultural competencies to appreciate their culture and heritage.

Teachers form the core of Singapore's education system. We are committed to nurturing and motivating our teachers to grow and reach their personal and professional best, in line with their aspirations and interests. Our teachers receive rigorous and evidence-based pre-service training at the National Institute of Education, and have many opportunities for in-service development to build up their competencies. Teacher academies, language institutes, and HQ divisions foster a strong culture of professional excellence underpinned by a philosophy of teacher ownership and teacher leadership. Another peculiarity of Singaporean education is the unusual evaluation system. In most educational institutions, students' learning level is measured on the basis of nine-point assessment criteria - A1 - (the highest), F9 - (the lowest). It includes A1/A2 (excellent), B3/B4 (good), C5/C6 (satisfactory), D7 (minimum score for subject mastery) and E8/F9 (unsatisfactory). The final rating results in schools are determined based on the accumulated points. In Singapore, the most gifted students can take the Integrated Program (IP). In this case, secondary school students in the country will be given the opportunity to take the A-level exam as soon as they complete 6 years of secondary education without having to pass the O-level exams. This opens the way for students to have more free time and study their chosen subjects more deeply.

Contract money paid for higher education in Great Britain, USA or Compared to Australia, it is several times cheaper in Singapore. But here it is the quality of education provided is not inferior to that of any European country. That's why many foreign young people study in educational institutions in Singapore. Continuing higher education in Singapore is not as complicated as many people think. For this, it is necessary to have a deep knowledge of the English language. Also from Singapore universities that he received primary and secondary education from foreign applicants who want to study in one of them certificate or diploma, IELTS confirming

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knowledge of the English language or TOEFL certificate is required. If there is no certificate, an applicant to get it He can study in one of the language teaching schools in Singapore. Singapore also has a wide range of educational grants for students. This Apply for any gifted student scholarship or grant can do. Grants from the state, educational institutions or employers financed. Read the amount of payment allocated to the students who won them fully covers expenses.

That is why Singapore's HEIs occupy high places in the world rankings Stands Having studied the dynamics of the development of the Singapore education system, we came to the following conclusion: social problems of Uzbekistan's education, universal, national and individual factors in education, developed countries classification using educational achievements, theory of education and choosing the universal advanced experience of practice, modern pedagogical ideas and development technology, the ability to use advanced experience and teaching technologies in the educational process, the world and our republic based on universal human values to be able to diagnose the development of education; compare the development of education in the world and in our republic analysis; to be able to see the advantages in the development of education of our republic and its acquisition of skills to predict future development, pedagogical work with literature; creating the necessary methodical instructions; effective pedagogy conducting research, being able to use the method of comparative analysis, in the process of comparative analysis skills to take into account the peculiarities in the development of world countries we need to have it.

References:

1. Anvar Khojaev, Singapore education system: becoming a leading brand in world education, Marifat newspaper, 11.01.2019
2. PISA. <http://www.education-medelle.com> (PISA Program of the International Monitoring System). Retrieved 18.09.2016
3. Pedagogy / Textbook / Prof. Under the general editorship of M.Kh. Tokhtakhodjayeva. - Tashkent: "National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan" publishing house, 2010.
4. Wolfson B.F. Sravnitel'naya pedagogika M.: "Prosveshchenie", 2003.